

CULTURAL CONFLICTS BETWEEN MOTHER AND DAUGHTER DEPICTED IN AMY TAN'S NOVEL "THE JOY LUCK CLUB"

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Abstract. This article explores the cultural conflicts depicted in Amy Tan's novel "The Joy Luck Club." Through an analysis of the intergenerational and intercultural tensions between Chinese immigrant mothers and their American-born daughters, the study delves into the complexities of identity, heritage, and assimilation. Tan's narrative vividly portrays the struggles migrants face while getting used to the new environment and lifestyle.

Keywords: mother and daughter, reader response theory, diaspora literature, identity crisis, national stereotypes.

Through the different approaches to sources of the contradiction between mother and daughter, Amy Tan's novel "The Joy Luck Club" opens a door for readers to know about the living background of Chinese Americans and their various experiences comprehensively. On the other hand, they provide us with a good perspective on the mother-daughter relationship in Chinese American families and even our own families. In exploring the root causes, the author also shows us the process of self-recognition. Knowing a mother is also the process of a daughter's self-awareness. In the era of globalization, culture is gradually becoming more diverse and inclusive. Cultural conflicts are no longer only a problem faced by Chinese American families, but also the reshaping of human souls, which has become a focus of social attention. In this sense, Amy Tan's exploration of mother-daughter relationships is somewhat enlightening. From confrontation to reconciliation is not only the requirements and inevitability of plot development, but also the author's emotional needs and expression. From Amy Tan's life information, we know that she had not yet fully understood her mother and realized what she inherited from her mother before her mother left. This became one of the causes of her confusion, so Amy Tan used her mother's stories to construct the stories of her novels, and through literary imagination, she fulfilled her unfulfilled wishes in the writing of a mother-daughter relationship with substitute wishes. The reconciliation model of the novel to some extent reflects the author's strong inner needs and unconscious creative pursuit. In *The Joy Luck Club*, Amy Tan wrote "To my mother and the memory of her mother"; in *The Kitchen God's Wife*, she wrote "To my mother, Daisy Tan, and her happy memories of my father, John (1914-1968) and my brother Peter (1950-1967) with love and respect."; in *The Bonesetter's Daughter*, she wrote, "On the last day that my mother spent on earth, I taught her real name, as well as that of my grandmother. This book is dedicated to them." Here we can see that the writer's unfulfilled wish was finally realized in the creation, completing the reconstruction of the mother-daughter relationship and family connection.

Therefore, in her novels, the obvious contradiction and conflicts between immigrant mothers and American daughters are finally resolved, and mother and daughter get reconciliation. Reconciliation cannot be achieved without mothers' strong love and good intentions towards their daughters. Whatever mothers and daughters have experienced, mothers have always kept strong love and good intentions to their daughters. Ying Ying told Jing-mei, "*Your mother was a very strong woman, a good mother. She loved you very much, more than her own life.*"¹ An-mei told her daughter Rose "*A mother is best. A mother knows what is inside you.*"² Therefore, the mothers wait for a proper time and chance to let the daughters know about their past and family lineage. The following are the approaches or efforts from both sides of mother and daughter, which contribute to the improvement and reconciliation of the relationship between mother and daughter.

On the side of the mother, it is the storytelling of her past. In *The Joy Luck Club*, the four mothers in turn tell the stories of their childhood, the stories of their marriage and experiences, and even the stories of their mothers. Their stories sound like a monologue, but the target listener is their daughters. Suyuan told her daughter Jing-mei many times about her experience during the wartime, how she managed a hopeful life with other female friends in Kweilin, how she had to escape from Kweilin to Chongqing, and what she saw and did on the way. Lindo told her daughter Waverly what she had experienced as a daughter-in-law since her two years old, and how she managed to escape from her unhappy sexless marriage. An-mei told her daughter Rose that she suffered from a pot of soup which left a forever scar on her neck, but it was nothing compared with her mother's suffering. Her mother was raped not long after her husband's death. What made the misfortune worse was that her family attributed the disgrace to her fault and drove her out of her family. In that case, she had to get married to the man who raped her as the fourth concubine with the lowest position in the family. After she gave birth to a son, the second wife took the boy away and made him her own son. Finally, she protested against suicide. Ying-Ying told her daughter Lena how she fell into a river and got lost when she was four years old, how she was betrayed by her husband and lost her innocence even herself, and how she killed her unborn baby for revenge and suffered the lasting torture even since then.

In *The Kitchen God's Wife*, Winnie told her daughter Pearl how her mother fell in love with a young journalist but was forced to get married to her father's old friend replacing his dead second wife. At Winnie's six years old, her mother finally decided to leave home mysteriously. Then Winnie was sent to her uncle's family by her father just because her father didn't want to see her anymore to remind her mother's disgrace. Living in a family not belonging to "the other" for twelve years, Winnie wanted to change her fate by marriage. Unfortunately, she falls into hell, suffering from her husband's humiliation, violence, rape and other tortures beyond words and imagination. In a terrible family situation, she lost her three children. It seemed there was no place for her to hide from her husband's chasing until she was sent to jail for two years. At last, Pearl was informed that her biological father was the first husband of her mother, a demonic man. Upon learning about her mother's past, Pearl not only got a deeper understanding of her mother but also found the strength and hope to overcome her disease. On the side of a daughter, it is their active inquiry into maternal lineage, seeking root in China,

¹ Amy Tan. *The Joy Luck Club*. London: Vintage, 2019. –p.33.

² Same source. –p.224.

willingly accepting the mother's suggestion and apology that counts more to the reconciliation of mother and daughter.

In the novels, during the daughters' growing up, they didn't understand why their mothers kept complaining, were unsatisfied with their performance, and always asked them to improve. Pearl didn't understand why her mother was so strict and demanding of her; Ruth didn't know why her mother was so irritable and worried. Not knowing the past of mothers resulted in a breakdown in emotional communication between mother and daughter. The rupture of family memory makes the daughter unable to recognize the Chinese elements in herself and unaware that there are also things in her personality that are similar to her mother's.

Адабиётлар руйхати:

1. Amy Tan. *The Joy Luck Club*. London: Vintage, 2019. –p.33.
2. Neelima V. Dual. *Consciousness Dilution of Dissent in Mother Daughter Relationship in the Select Works of Amy Tan*. University of Calicut, 2018. –240 P.
3. Nomita Loktongbam. *Identity Formation in Amy Tans Select Works*. Loktongbam, Anna University, 2016. –150 P.
4. Paul Ricoeur *Time and Narrative, Volume 3*, Translated by Kathleen Blamey and David Pellaver, Chicago and London, The University of Chicago Press. 1990.
5. Percy Lubbock. *The Craft of Fiction*. New York: Viking Press, 1957. –237 P.
6. Priyadharshini C.P.C. *Journey towards A New Dawn in the Select Novels of Amy Tan and Jhumpa Lahiri*. Bharathiar University, 2019. –260 P.